

Spectrophotometric Determination of Dinocap in Water and Spray Residues

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Many methods based on spectrophotometry¹, hplc² and tlc³ are reported for the determination of dinocap, a contact fungicide with protective and curative action⁴. Dinocap is highly toxic to human and warm blooded animals (tolerance limit in fruit is 0.1 mg/kg)⁵. Here we report, a new method based on the reduction of dinocap, i.e. 2,4-dinitro-6-octylphenyl crotonate to 2,4-diamino-6-octylphenyl crotonate by Zn/HCl and coupling of the reduced compound with NEDA, i.e. *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride, after diazotisation.

Results and Discussion

Dinocap was completely reduced with zinc dust (250 mg) and 1 M HCl (1 ml). Excess of HCl did not interfere in the reaction.

Diazotisation and coupling: Constant absorbance values were obtained when 1–8 ml of nitrite was used. Acidity during diazotisation was maintained with 0.3–4M HCl. Studies on the effect of time on diazotisation reaction showed that there was no significant change in absorbance value from 2 to 60 min. The effect of amount of NEDA on coupling reaction was also studied and 1 ml of NEDA was found to be the best for coupling. ~ 15 min time was needed for full colour development.

Spectral characteristics: All spectral studies were carried out at 545 nm in a final solution volume of 10 ml containing various amount of dinocap. The violet dye was stable for 12 h. The colour reaction obeys Beer's law in the range 4.8–33.6 ppm of dinocap. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $9.1 \times 10^3 (\pm 100) \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.04 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The reproducibility of the method was checked by analysing a solution containing 192 μg of dinocap per 10 ml for a period of 8 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.0125 and $\pm 2.5\%$ respectively.

Effect of contaminants: The effects of various

interfering copollutants and pesticides were studied in order to assess the validity of the method. Known amounts of metal ions and pesticides were added to the sample solution and dinocap was determined by the proposed method. The tolerance limit (in ppm) for foreign species in a solution containing 192 μg of dinocap per 10 ml are as follows: ions Sn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mg^{II} and phosphate (500); Fe^{II} , Ca^{II} and Al^{III} (250), and pesticides Zineb and Mancozeb (1000); Captan and Folpet (750); 2-4-D and 2,4,5-T (800), Parathion methyl (100); Malathion, Carbaryl and Propoxur (500); DDT and BHC (700), Endosulphan (850). The nitro containing pesticides which behave similar to dinocap are likely to cause interference.

TABLE I—RECOVERY OF DINOCAP FROM WATER AND SPRAY RESIDUES*

Sample	Dinocap (μg)		% Recovery
	Added	Found	
Water	48	41.20	85.83
	96	90.10	93.85
	192	182.40	95.00
Apple	48	42.50	88.54
	96	89.30	93.02
	192	181.00	94.27
Grape	48	41.82	87.12
	96	88.80	92.50
	192	182.20	94.89

* Mean of three replicate analysis.

Application:

Determination of dinocap in water: Water samples (100 ml) from the nearby fields where dinocap was sprayed were collected. Dinocap was extracted with benzene (2×20 ml). The benzene extract was evaporated under reduced pressure to obtain a solid residue containing dinocap. This residue was dissolved in ethanol and analysed by the proposed method. To check the recovery, known amounts of dinocap was added to the water samples. This was kept for 2 h and dinocap was analysed by the proposed method. The recoveries ranging from 85–95% were obtained (Table 1).

Determination of dinocap in fruits : Different samples (100 g each) of apples and grapes were collected from the market, which were treated with dinocap. These were washed well with ethanol (2×20 ml). The washings were analysed by the proposed as well as earlier reported method⁵ and the results were found to be in good agreement. The dinocap found in these samples was from 58 to 96 μg in 100 g of fruits. Recoveries were checked by crushing the apples and grapes (100 g) and adding known amounts of dinocap. These were filtered after 2 h and the filtrate was analysed by the proposed method. Recoveries ranging from 85 to 95% were obtained (Table 1).

The proposed method is simple, rapid, reproducible and can be successfully applied for the determination of dinocap in water and spray residues.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss Specol spectrophotometer with 1-cm matched silica cell was used for spectral measurements. A standard dinocap solution (Indofil Chemical Ltd.) (1 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared in ethanol and a working standard ($192 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution⁴. A 0.2% solution of NEDA was prepared in water. All reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Demineralised water was used throughout the experiment.

Procedure : Aliquots containing 4.8–33.6 ppm of

dinocap was reduced by zinc dust ($\sim 250 \text{ mg}$) and HCl. After 5 min, the solution was filtered and the residue washed with $1M$ HCl (2 ml). Both the filtrate and washings were transferred quantitatively. To the reduced dinocap, nitrite solution (1 ml) was added and kept for 2 min for complete diazotisation. The excess of nitrite was removed by addition of a few drops of H_2SO_4 . This was followed by addition of NEDA solution (1 ml). The solution was then kept for ~ 15 min to complete the coupling reaction and made upto 10 ml with $2M$ HCl. The absorbance of the purple dye was measured at 545 nm against the reagent blank.

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